

METHODS AND TIMING FOR PROPAGATING RED CURRANT VARIETIES THROUGH SEEDLINGS

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Abstract. The propagation of seedlings of introduced red currant varieties grown in the conditions of the Tashkent region, optimal timing, and optimal soil environment are described.

Keywords: Soil environment, peat, cocopeat, cuttings, variant, calus, root, variety, "cherry red", "Rovada", "Heros", "Honeywood".

Introduction. In recent years, special attention has been paid in our republic to the development of fruit growing, the expansion of fruit assortments, the increase in export volumes, and the gradual transition from low-productivity extensive orchards to high-efficiency intensive orchards. In this context, the assortment of berry crops that are important for the traditional horticulture of the republic is being expanded through the introduction of species and varieties imported from abroad. For the establishment of such berry plantations, the selection of varieties distinguished by valuable economic traits and the application of advanced cultivation technologies are of great importance. In 2025, a number of significant Decrees (PF) and Resolutions (PQ) related to agriculture were adopted in Uzbekistan. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-131 dated March 28, 2025, "On Additional Measures to Increase the Efficiency of Land Use in Agriculture and Expand Agricultural Production," focuses on organizing crop cultivation and production on unused agricultural lands, stimulating efficient land use through economic mechanisms, and ultimately increasing employment and improving the living standards of the population.

Today, a range of scientific and practical efforts are being undertaken to enhance the economic efficiency of fruit growing and expand its assortment in order to ensure food security and establish the foundations of healthy nutrition for the population. In this regard, in-depth scientific research is being carried out to improve the technological elements of red currant berry production and to develop new varieties with an even richer biochemical composition, particularly those high in vitamin C and provitamin A.

Materials and methods. The experiments were conducted based on the methodological guide by M. T. Tarasenko, "New Technology for Plant Propagation by Green Cuttings" (1969). Experiments aimed at developing methods for propagating red currant varieties through seedlings and introducing them into production were carried out on four newly introduced varieties.

New red currant varieties are developed through seed propagation. However, for the multiplication of new varieties, vegetative propagation—primarily by cuttings taken from one-year-old shoots—is widely used.

Under the hot and arid climatic conditions of Uzbekistan, studies were conducted on irrigated lands to determine the most suitable timing for preparing and planting red currant cuttings. Cuttings were prepared from one-year-old shoots of red currant plants. In winter, on January 20, cuttings from four introduced varieties were prepared and planted in four different soil media. When preparing cuttings from one-year-old shoots, their length ranged from 18 to 25 cm, with a diameter of about 0.6 cm. The cuttings were taken from healthy, well-grown bushes and from one-year-old shoots that were dark brown or gray in color. Cuttings obtained from immature shoots root poorly and often perish. Diseased, crooked shoots, those with darkened cores, or shoots affected by wilt were discarded. When cutting the shoots, the upper cut was made at a 45° angle above the bud, while the lower cut was made straight below the bud. Observations were carried out accordingly.

Results and discussion. Cuttings obtained from one-year-old seedlings of red currant varieties were studied under experimental conditions to evaluate their growth and development in four different soil media: peat, cocopeat, a mixture of peat and cocopeat, and ordinary soil.

For each variety, 40 cuttings were prepared and planted in pots containing four different soil media. The cuttings were prepared on January 20, with a length of 18–25 cm and a diameter of about 0.6 cm. From each variety, 40 cuttings were taken and planted as follows: 10 cuttings in peat (Variant I), 10 cuttings in cocopeat (Variant II), 10 cuttings in a peat–cocopeat mixture (Variant III), and 10 cuttings in ordinary soil (Variant IV). Their growth and development were monitored throughout the experiment.

Red currant cuttings began to form callus tissue at the basal part after 45–50 days. By days 50–55, white absorbing roots appeared. To obtain healthy, standard seedlings, it is essential to have a good understanding of appropriate planting times and methods. Among all the studied red currant varieties, autumn was identified as the most favorable period for preparing and planting cuttings. Cuttings prepared in winter and planted directly without storage in trenches also showed good establishment.

Analysis of biometric data indicated that cuttings prepared and planted in autumn produced significantly stronger seedlings across all varieties. When autumn is dry and warm and spring is also dry, it is necessary to irrigate red currant cuttings after planting and to maintain the soil in a loose and moist condition during the growing period. Depending on soil moisture, the cuttings were irrigated 8–12 times. During the growing season, irrigation was carried out twice in May, 2–3 times in June, 2–3 times in July, 1–2 times in August, and once in September, for a total of 8–12 irrigations. During irrigation, the soil in the pots was kept loose at all times and regularly cleared of weeds.

During irrigation, the soil moisture in Variants I and III remained consistently within optimal levels, whereas drying of the soil medium was observed in Variants II and IV. According to the results of the experiments conducted on cuttings planted in pots during winter, 100% sprouting was observed in all four variants (see Table 1).

Table 1

Option No	Varieties	Callus formation time	The period of time when the sucker formed roots	Leaf swelling	Writing of leaves
I	Chery red	15.03.2025	30.03.2025	10.04.2025	22.04.2025
	Heros	20.03.2025	02.04.2025	13.04.2025	21.04.2025
	Rovada	18.03.2025	05.04.2025	15.04.2025	24.04.2025
	Honeywood	19.03.2025	05.04.2025	16.04.2025	26.04.2025
II	Chery red	20.03.2025	05.04.2025	14.04.2025	28.04.2025
	Heros	23.03.2025	10.04.2025	21.04.2025	30.04.2025
	Rovada	25.03.2025	18.04.2025	22.04.2025	02.05.2025
	Honeywood	27.03.2025	21.04.2025	27.04.2025	02.05.2025
III	Chery red	14.03.2025	28.03.2025	09.04.2025	19.04.2025
	Heros	15.03.2025	28.03.2025	13.04.2025	22.04.2025
	Rovada	18.03.2025	01.04.2025	12.04.2025	25.04.2025
	Honeywood	20.03.2025	03.04.2025	12.04.2025	26.04.2025
IV	Chery red	25.03.2025	11.04.2025	19.04.2025	28.04.2025
	Heros	27.03.2025	13.04.2025	23.04.2025	28.04.2025
	Rovada	27.03.2025	18.04.2025	26.04.2025	03.05.2025
	Honeywood	27.03.2025	20.04.2025	30.04.2025	05.05.2025

During the experimental study, it was observed that red currant cuttings planted in 4 variants developed better than those planted in peat.

It was observed that the growth and development of red currant cuttings planted in 4 different soil media, the vegetation period in seedlings planted in peat began earlier and the seedlings grew and developed faster.

Conclusion and recommendations. In conclusion, the study showed that when the cuttings were planted in four different soil media, rooting reached 100% in all variants. Among them, in Variant I, the Cherry Red cultivar was observed to root earlier (15/III). The growing season also began earlier in this cultivar, as early bud swelling was recorded on 10/IV. At the same time, in Variant III, earlier rooting was also observed in the Cherry Red, Heros, and Rovada cultivars.

In Variants II and IV, the cuttings rooted later compared with those planted in Variants I and III. In Variant IV, i.e., in ordinary soil, the rooting date of Honeywood cuttings was recorded 65–70 days after planting (20/IV).

To promote earlier rooting of cuttings, it is recommended to plant them in the soil media used in Variants I and III—peat and the peat–cocopeat mixture.

Figure 1. Irrigation process of red currant cuttings

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